

Software Categories and Lifecycle Stages

Used in the registration form of the 2024 Software for the NASA SMD workshop.

Software Categories

- Mission-related software
- Code associated with research (e.g. for publications)
- Data repository software (e.g. infrastructure software, cloud services, software environments)
- Archiving software (in a FAIR manner, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>)
- Analysis libraries or domain libraries (e.g. SolarSoft, XSPEC, Sunpy, Astropy)
- Software related to models and simulations (including pre and post processing and visualization codes)
- ML/AI codes
- General analysis software for wide use (e.g. SciPy)
- Infrastructure as code, and web or cloud applications
- High performance computing

Lifecycle Stages

- Discovery vs acquisition vs collaboration for software
- Funding software effectively
- Designing/developing software
- Developing vs contributing to software
- When to choose open or closed software?
- Releasing software (e.g. the Software Release Authorization process)
- Maintaining software, confirming reproducibility/reusability
- Retiring software
- Building, fostering, and managing software communities and collaborations
- Security and supply chain risk management
- Complying with policies (e.g. NPR 7150, NASA policies, etc)
- Formulating and aligning with best practices and standards for software